

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Modeling Current Energy Converters in the Tanana River near Nenana, Alaska: A Comparison of Simulated Data and ADCP Measurements

Emily Browning^{ab*}, Sterling Olson^a, James McVey^c, Rebecca Fao^d, Adam Keester^a

^aWater Power Technologies, Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM, USA

^bUniversity of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK 99775, USA

^cCoastal Sciences Division, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, Seattle, WA, United States

^dWater Power, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Golden, CO, United States

Abstract

Modeling is a cost-effective approach for understanding numerous Current Energy Converter (CEC) deployments, enabling the optimization of infrastructure and resource allocation before implementation. However, to maximize the benefits of modeling, it is crucial to incorporate experimental data to enhance accuracy. In this study, we use the Tanana River Test site near Nenana, Alaska, as a test case to compare Delft3D simulations with Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) measurements. The test site has been employed over the past decade to deploy and evaluate various CEC devices, with datasets including extensively documented bathymetry surveys, and velocity measurements before and during CEC deployments. This study demonstrates methods for refining a Delft3D model to better represent a transect ADCP measurement before a CEC deployment.

Keywords: MHKiT; marine energy; Tanana River; Delft3D; ADCP; transect; DOLfYN

1. Introduction

Alaska is ranked #2 for highest energy cost in the USA, with many Alaskan communities having energy prices two to three times the state average due to their remote locations, in many cases only being accessible by boat or plane [1,2]. Of these remote communities, over 200 of them are near a potential water energy source [2, 3]. Due to the remote nature of these communities, new energy technology must be rigorously tested prior to deployment as maintenance will be costly or not an option. The Alaska Center for Energy and Power (ACEP) ran into several issues during two remote CEC deployments in Ruby and Eagle leading them to establish the Tanana River Test Site (TRTS) [4,5]. The TRTS is centrally located in Alaska and connected to the road system, making the TRTS easily accessible from the University of Alaska Fairbanks. Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) transects are one of the main methods ACEP uses to characterize and monitor TRTS river conditions like river velocities [7] and site assessments [6]. Beyond site assessments, these transects can be used in a predictive manner using modeling tools such as SNL-Delft3D-CEC-FM which allow the user to predict how river conditions and current energy converters (CEC) interact. These modeling efforts can help interested parties understand the impacts, such as environmental impacts and power production, a CEC or an array of CECs may have on the river over extended operating periods.

Previous work in [9] demonstrated the use of a free and open-source software, MHKiT, to process and compare both ADCP transects and Delft3D modeled data. Conveniently, this data is provided in the MHKiT GitHub repository allowing other to reproduce and modify this software for their needs. The previous work found significant error, 25%

to 30%, between model and transect data. This research builds on the open-source data of the previous research and discusses the process of refining the Delft3D model to improve the agreement between the model and the transect data.

2. Data Collection and Model Design

The transect data compared with the model was averaged between two transect passes, Fig 1 (Left), to create a linear best fit. The averaged data is used to produce a contour plot of velocity throughout the cross-sectional area of the river, shown in Fig. 1 (Right).

Fig. 1. (Left) TRTS aerial view overlaid with two vessel transects. The arrow shows the direction of the river flow.[9] The barge and CEC deployment shown was not present while the transects shown were being measured. (Right) Velocity magnitude collected by an ADCP linearly interpolated onto an ideal linear transect.[9]

To simulate the river velocity at the TRTS the software Delft3D is used because in addition to being a popular environmental modeling tool, it is open-source and researchers at Sandia National Laboratories have modified the source code to simulate turbines released as SNL-Delft3D-CEC-FM. The inputs needed to start modeling are quite simple: bathymetry, discharge, and water level. The bathymetry data was collected on the same day as a set of transects August 10th, 2010 [10] and records from the USGS monitoring station water level (2.7 m) and discharge (1789 m³/s) were collected [11]. Once the Delft3D model was run MHKiT was used to extract a transect to compare to the ADCP field data.

3. Refining the Delft3D Model

Here we will use two metrics, the L_1 norm, equation (1), and the L_2 norm, equation (2), as a measure of model accuracy between Delft3D and the ADCP transects for the velocity magnitude. Errors are expressed as fractions of their experimental value. In each equation below D3D (Delft3D) and ADCP refer to the source the velocity magnitude data was collected from.

$$L_1 = \frac{|D3D-ADCP|}{ADCP} \quad (1)$$

$$L_2 = \left(\frac{D3D-ADCP}{ADCP} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Nomenclature

L_1	L_1 error norm
L_2	L_2 error norm
D3D	modeled velocity magnitude
ADCP	measured velocity magnitude

The first investigation of the model concerned the water level input to Delft3D. The initial model was created with a water level of 2.7m based on the USGS data. Upon further investigation of the raw bathymetry data the ADCP depth was consistently 2.9m greater in magnitude over 3 transects. Since the water level is set at the outlet and calculated throughout the rest of the river the water level of 1.8m got the closest to reproducing the depth recorded by the ADCP, shown in figure 2 (left).

Fig.2 . (Left) ADCP measured depth vs raw bathymetry depth (Right) ADCP measured depth vs depth from the water surface with a 1.8m initial water level.

The compared L_1 , and L_2 for the different water levels are shown in Table 1. Correcting the water level has decreased L_1 by almost 10%. From these corrected results it's still apparent the boundary layer at the river bottom is not properly being simulated with the highest error values being located at the river bottom, shown in figure 3. However, being able to increase the accuracy of the midstream flow is an improvement to previous iterations.

Table 1. Average L_1 and L_2 error values with different Water levels values.

Water Level	Average L_1	Average L_2
2.7 meter	0.270	0.111
1.8 meter	0.183	0.062

Fig.3 . L_1 error value contour of ideal linear transect area.

4. Conclusion

The TRTS site is an important CEC test site which can help bring Alaskans clean, reliable energy and help bring CECs to market. As such the creation of an open-source TRTS predictive model which researchers and device manufactures can use is invaluable as it will allow for rapid testing and adjustments, and as a foundation for manufactures to use in the site permitting process should they be looking for a production installation. This TRTS case details the current steps taken in providing the world with an open-source model of the TRST. The long-term goals are to provide a model with a 1 m discretization to match the size of most turbines tested at TRTS. Once lower grid discretization and validation with collected transects is achieved, the SNL-Delft3D-CEC-FM software will be used to create arrays of CECs which will enable studies around the environmental impacts of these devices in Alaska's river systems.

Acknowledgements

The data used for this study was collected by the Alaska Center for Energy and Power by Paul DUVOY and Jack Schmid funded by the Alaska Energy Authority 2195437/G00005572.\

Sandia National Laboratories is a multimission laboratory managed and operated by National Technology and Engineering Solutions of Sandia, LLC, a wholly owned subsidiary of Honeywell International Inc., for the U.S. Department of Energy's National Nuclear Security Administration under contract DE-NA0003525.

This work was authored in part by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory, operated by Alliance for Sustainable Energy, LLC, for the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) under Contract No. DE-AC36-08GO28308, and the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, operated by Battelle Memorial Institute for the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) under Contract No. DE-AC05-76RL01830.

Funding provided by the U.S. Department of Energy Office of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Water Power Technologies Office. Any subjective views or opinions that might be expressed in the paper do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Department of Energy or the United States Government. The U.S. Government retains and the publisher, by accepting the article for publication, acknowledges that the U.S. Government retains a nonexclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, worldwide license to publish or reproduce the published form of this work, or allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes.

References

- [1] Townsend, Quinn. "Alaska's Electricity Prices, Ranked: Alaska Policy Forum." Alaska Policy Forum | Our Vision Is an Alaska That Continuously Grows Prosperity by Maximizing Individual Opportunities and Freedom, 7 Dec. 2022, alaskapolicyforum.org/2022/12/alaskas-electricity-prices-ranked/#:~:text=According%20to%20a%20recent%20report,per%20kWh%2C%20below%20only%20Hawaii.
- [2] G. P. Holdmann, R. W. Wies, and J. B. Vandermeer, "Renewable Energy Integration in Alaska's Remote Islanded Microgrids: Economic Drivers, Technical Strategies, Technological Niche Development, and Policy Implications," Proceedings of the IEEE, vol. 107, no. 9, pp. 1820–1837, 2019.
- [3] Kao, Shih-Chieh, et al. *New stream-reach development: a comprehensive assessment of hydropower energy potential in the United States*. No. ORNL/TM-2013/514. Oak Ridge National Lab.(ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN (United States), 2014.
- [4] Johnson, Jerome B., and Dominique J. Pride. "River, tidal, and ocean current hydrokinetic energy technologies: status and future opportunities in Alaska." *Prepared for Alaska Center for Energy and Power* (2010).

- [5] J. B. Johnson, H. Toniolo, A. C. Seitz, J. Schmid, P. Duvoy, and A. Hydrokinetic, "Characterization of the Tanana River at Nenana , Alaska , to Determine the Important Factors Affecting Site Selection , Deployment , and Operation of Hydrokinetic Devices to Generate Power Prepared by," no. March, 2013.
- [6] T.Ravens, "Alaska In-River Hydrokinetic Energy Resources," University of Alaska Anchorage 2014.
- [7] Mueller, David S., et al. Measuring discharge with acoustic Doppler current profilers from a moving boat. Reston, Virginia (EUA): US Department of the Interior, US Geological Survey, 2009.
- [8] Browning, E.; Olson, S. ADCP Delft3D TRTS Example. Available online: https://github.com/MHkiT-Software/MHkiT-Python/blob/master/examples/ADCP_Delft3D_TRTS_example.ipynb (accessed on 26 January 2023).
- [9] Browning, Emily, et al. "Tanana River Test Site Model Verification Using the Marine and Hydrokinetic Toolkit (MHkiT)." *Energies* 16.8 (2023): 3326.
- [10] TerraSond. ORPC Hydrokinetic Power Production Project Physical Characterization Survey Tanana River at Nenana, Alaska. TerraSond Ltd. 2011
- [11] TANANA R AT NENANA AK. Available online: <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/15515500/#parameterCode=00065&period=P7D>